

Mutations in LRRK2 impair NF- κ B pathway in iPSC-derived neurons

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Additional Material.

Target gene	Forward (5'-3')	Reverse (5'-3')
PTGS1 (COX-1)	CGATGCATACACCACATGAA	AGCGAAGGCTTCTCAAATCA
PTGS2 (COX-2)	GAATCATTACACCAGGCAAATTG	TCTGTACTGCGGGTGAACA
GAPDH	TGCACCACCAACTGCTTAGC	GGCATGGACTGTGGTCATGAG
GFAP	TCTCTCGGAGTATCTGGAACTG	TTCCCTTCCTGTCTGAGTCTCA
IL6	ATGCAATAACCACCCCT	AGTGCCTAACGCTCATAAC
LRRK2	TCCAGATCAACCAAGGCTCACCAT	AGGCTGCTCGGTAAACTGATCCAA
MAPT	GATTGGGTCCCTGGACAATA	GTGGTCTGTCTTGGCTTTGG
NFKBIA (I κ B α)	GATCCGCCAGGTGAAGG	GCAATTTCTGGCTGGTTGG
PINK1	GCTTGGGACCTCTCTTGGAT	CGAAGCCATCTTGAACACAA
SNCA	TCCAGAATTCCTTCCTGTGG	GAAGACAGTGGAGGGAGCAG
TNFAIP3 (A20)	GTCCGGAAGCTTGTGGCGCT	CCAAGTCTGTGTCTGAACGCCC
TNFRSF1A (TNFR1)	AATGCCGAAAGGAAATGGGTCAGG	AGGTGCACACGGTGTCTGTTTCT
TNFRSF1B (TNFR2)	TGGTGTGAAAGTCAGATGCCAGA	TGGCAGAGTTTGGCTTTGTCGTTG
TH	TGTCTGAGGAGCCTGAGATTCG	GCTTGTCTTGGCGTCACTG
TUJ1	AGTCGCCCACGTAGTTGC	CGCCAGTATGAGGGAGAT

Additional Table 1. Primer sequences used in RT-qPCR analyses.